

**DETECTION OF ANEMIA AMONG LEUKEMIA PATIENTS DEPENDING ON
DEPENDS ON GENDER AND AGE.****Suleymanova D.N., Ulugova Sh.T.**

Resume. The research was conducted on the basis of retrospective material, 505 case histories of treated leukemia patients in the clinic of the Russian National Cancer Center for 5 years - 2019-2023 were studied. Venous blood of patients was used to diagnose anemia, and tests were performed on a mindray Vs-5600 hematology analyzer. The results showed that the lowest number of treated leukemia patients was detected in the post-covid period - 2022, only 13% of the total number of patients, and the largest number of patients in 2020-2021 during the Covid-19 epidemic, which amounted to 23.96% and 22.57%. Among the treated patients with leukemia, the number of men prevails compared to women - 55.65% and 44.35%, respectively, and the indicators over the years also confirm these data. A comparison of anemia rates over 5 years has shown that the level of anemia in 2020-2021 (Covid-19 epidemic) was 95.04% and 93.86%, which is significantly higher than in 2019 – 90.63% (pre-epidemic period). A study of the rates of treated leukemia patients over 5 years, depending on age, showed that men predominate in the age group of 44-60 years – 58%, in the age groups of 45-60 years and 61-75 years, men also predominate – 54.90% and 53.68%. At the age of 76-81, the number of men was significantly less than that of women and amounted to 43.75%.

Relevance. Anemia is a clinical and hematological syndrome characterized by a decrease in the concentration of hemoglobin and red blood cells per unit volume of blood. Anemia of chronic diseases or anemia of inflammation is a common type of anemia that develops in patients with infectious, inflammatory, or malignant diseases, including leukemia. The etiology of anemia of chronic diseases is multifaceted and insufficiently studied. Until recently, the molecular mechanisms and pathogenesis of iron distribution disorders in anemia of chronic diseases were unknown. However, research in recent decades has made it possible to establish multifactorial pathophysiological mechanisms of anemia in chronic diseases. Thus, the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines in acute infection or chronic disease can alter the systemic metabolism of iron through excessive synthesis of the key iron-regulatory hormone hepcidin. In addition, hepcidin inhibits the export of iron from cells, blocking the activity of ferroportin, and excess hepcidin is the primary cause of a decrease in serum iron and, in this regard, a violation of normal erythropoiesis observed in anemia of chronic diseases. Experimental data indicate a significant role of hepcidin in functional iron deficiency observed in anemia of chronic diseases. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is often associated with various chronic diseases, including oncological and oncohematological (leukemia, myeloma, myelodysplastic syndrome, etc.). The development of anemic syndrome and iron metabolism in patients with hemoblastosis, and in particular leukemia, have been insufficiently studied and have contradictory opinions. These studies are devoted to the detection of anemia in patients with leukemia over 5 years, and to the study of the relationship between anemia indicators, gender and age of patients.

Materials and methods. The case histories of 505 leukemia patients treated at the hematology clinic in 2019-2023 served as research material. Of these, 225 are women. 280 are men. Urban patients 240, rural 265. The age of the patients is 18-81 years. The analyses were performed from the venous blood of patients with the mindray Vs-5600 hematology analyzer.

Results and discussion. The study of the dynamics of treated leukemia patients in the clinic of the Russian National Cancer Center in 2019-2023 is presented below. A comparative assessment of indicators was carried out depending on gender and age, as well as indicators of anemia.

Table 1

Indicators of treated leukemia patients in the clinic of the Russian National Cancer Center for 2019-2023, depending on gender

№	Years	Total		Women		Men	
		abs	%	abs	%	abs	%
1	2019	96	19,01	44	45,83	52	54,17
2	2020	121	23,96	51	42,15	70	57,85
3	2021	114	22,57	56	49,12	58	50,88
4	2022	68	13,47	29	42,65	39	57,35
5	2023	106	20,99	44	41,51	62	58,49
	Total	505	100,00	224	44,35	281	55,65

In just 5 years, 505 patients with leukemia were treated, of which 96 were in 2019, 121 in 2020, 114 in 2021, 68 in 2022, 106 in 2023. As can be seen from the data, the largest number of patients were treated in 2020-2021, which coincides with the Covid-19 epidemic. The fewest patients were treated in 2022, only 13% of the total number of patients, compared to 2020-2021, which amounted to 23.96% and 22.57%. In the post-covid period (2023), the figures were 20.99%. Thus, the Covid-19 epidemic correlates with the number of leukemia patients treated, which requires more in-depth research on the relationship between the incidence of leukemia and Covid-19. Perhaps there is a relationship with the state of the immune system and its effect on hematopoiesis. Comparative data between the indicators of women and men show that among the treated patients with leukemia, the number of men prevails - 55.65% and 44.35%, respectively, the difference is significant. The year-over-year dynamics also confirm these data.

Table 2

Detection of anemia in patients with leukemia depending on gender

№	Years	Total	one of them is anemia abs /%	Total Women	one of them is anemia abs /%	Total Men	one of them is anemia abs /%
1	2019	96	87 90,63	44	39 88,64	52	48 92,31

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2	2020	121	115 95,04	51	51 100,00	70	64 91,43
3	2021	114	107 93,86	56	54 96,43	58	53 91,38
4	2022	68	63 92,65	29	27 93,10	39	36 92,31
5	2023	106	100 94,34	44	41 93,18	62	59 95,16
	Total	505	472 93,47	224	212 94,64	281	260 92,53

Of the 505 patients with leukemia, anemia was detected in 472, which was 93.47%. A study of the data depending on gender showed that among women, anemia rates were 94.64%, among men 92.53%, the difference is unreliable. A comparison of anemia rates over 5 years has shown that the level of anemia in 2020-2021 (Covid-19 epidemic) was 95.04% and 93.86%, which is significantly higher than in 2019 – 90.63% (pre-epidemic period). Thus, anemia rates in leukemia patients correlate with the period of the Covid-19 epidemic, which requires deeper research into the relationship between anemia and the Covid-19 epidemic.

Studying the dynamics of anemia in men and women over 5 years suggests that 88.64% of women had anemia in the precancerous period, and in 2020 and 2021 it was significantly higher - 100% and 96.43%. In men, such a correlation was not found: in the pre-covid period, anemia was 92.31%, and in the years of the Covid-19 epidemic, 2020-2021, 91.43% and 91.38%, respectively. Thus, the Covid-19 epidemic correlates with anemia rates in women, but there is no such correlation in men.

A study of the rates of treated leukemia patients over 5 years, depending on age, showed that men predominate in the age group of 44-60 years – 58%, in the age groups of 45-60 years and 61-75 years, men also predominate – 54.90% and 53.68%. At the age of 76-81 years, the number of men was significantly less than that of women and amounted to 43.75%. The dynamics of male and female leukemia patients treated over 5 years showed the predominance of the number of men in all age categories.

Conclusions.

1. The lowest number of treated leukemia patients was detected in the post-covid period - 2022, only 13% of the total number of patients, and the largest number of patients in 2020-2021 during the Covid-19 epidemic, which amounted to 23.96% and 22.57%.
2. Among the treated patients with leukemia, the number of men prevails compared to women - 55.65% and 44.35%, respectively, and the indicators over the years also confirm these data.
3. A comparison of anemia indicators over 5 years has shown that the level of anemia in 2020-2021 (Covid-19 epidemic) was 95.04% and 93.86%, which is significantly higher than in 2019 – 90.63% (pre-epidemic period).
4. The study of the indicators of treated leukemia patients in dynamics over 5 years, depending on age, showed that men predominate in the age group of 44-60 years – 58%, in the age groups of 45-60 years and 61-75 years, men also predominate – 54.90% and 53.68%. At the age of 76-81, the number of men was significantly less than that of women and amounted to 43.75%.

Literature.

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